

**ANCIENT WISDOM ON DARUHARIDRA (*BERBERIS* SPP.): A
REVIEW OF AYURVEDIC AND PHARMACOLOGICAL
PERSPECTIVES**

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ABSTRACT

Daruharidra (commonly identified with *Berberis* species) holds an distinguish position in the Ayurvedic materia medica. References to this plant span from the Vedic era to later medieval texts, reflecting its continuous recognition and therapeutic importance in Indian medical traditions. This article reviews the documentation of *Daruharidra* in major Ayurvedic treatises, including the Vedas, Brihat Trayi (the three great treatises of Ayurveda), Laghu Trayi (Madhava Nidana, Sharngadhara Samhita, Bhavaprakasha) covers materia medica and therapeutics., and other classical compendia. Its repeated mention across diverse contexts, pharmacological properties, disease management, and formulation inclusion, illustrates its historical significance. By collating these references into a comprehensive master table, the study highlights the textual evidence for *Daruharidra*'s medicinal relevance, thereby providing a foundation for future pharmacological and clinical explorations.

KEYWORDS: *Daruharidra*, *Berberis*, Ayurveda, Brihat Trayi, Classical texts.

INTRODUCTION

Daruharidra (*Berberis* spp.) is one of the most revered medicinal plants in Ayurveda, frequently mentioned in classical texts for its wide spectrum of therapeutic applications. Its etymology derives from the Sanskrit terms Darvi (wood/stem) and Haridra (turmeric), suggesting “wood resembling turmeric” due to its characteristic yellow-colored stem and roots. Traditionally, it is valued for its potent Tikta Rasa (bitter taste), Katu Vipaka (pungent post-digestive effect), Ushna Virya (hot potency), and Kapha-Pitta Hara (alleviator of Kapha and Pitta doshas) properties, which make it effective in managing a broad range of disorders.

The significance of Daruharidra can be traced throughout the Brihat Trayi (the three great treatises of Ayurveda) namely, Charaka Samhita, Sushruta Samhita, and Ashtanga Hridaya as well as in Ashtanga Sangraha. Each of these texts, composed in different periods and contexts, highlight distinctive aspects of its medicinal applications. While Charaka Samhita (focused on Kayachikitsa, internal medicine) extensively recommends Daruharidra in conditions such as Kushta (skin disorders), Prameha (urinary disorders/diabetes), arsha (piles), Atisara (diarrhea), and Pandu (anemia), Sushruta Samhita (primarily surgical) emphasizes its role in Vrana (wound healing), Netra Roga (eye diseases), and Visha Chikitsa (toxicology). Similarly, Ashtanga Hridaya incorporates both internal and external therapeutic uses, whereas Ashtanga Sangraha expands its application to preventive and lifestyle regimens such as Shodhana (purificatory therapies) and Snana (bath rituals). In addition to its therapeutic versatility, Daruharidra is also notable for its numerous synonyms, including Darvi, Haridre, Katankateri, Rasanjana, Darunisha, Rajanidvaya, and Kaliyaka, which reflect regional variations in identification and usage across the Indian subcontinent. This multiplicity of references indicates the widespread acceptance of Daruharidra as a panacea-like drug in ancient India.

A comparative study of its descriptions in the Brihat-trayi and allied texts not only highlights the continuity of its use across centuries but also reveals the context-specific preferences of different schools of Ayurveda. Such an exploration provides valuable insight into the historical evolution of pharmacotherapy in Ayurveda and establishes a foundation for correlating its traditional applications with modern pharmacological investigations.

DARUHARIDRA IN Ancient Period

Daruharidra (*Berberis* spp.) holds an eminent position in Ayurveda, with extensive references across the Brihat-trayi and allied classical compendia. A critical survey of textual evidence

reveals that Charaka Samhita describes it under Arshoghna (anti-hemorrhoidal), Kandughna (anti-pruritic), Lekhaniya Mahakashaya (anti-obesity/scraping group of drugs) and Tikta Skandha (bitter group of drugs), prescribing it mainly for Kushta (skin disorders), Prameha (urinary disorders/diabetes), Arsha (piles/haemorrhoids), Atisara (diarrhoea), Pandu (anaemia), Netra Roga (eye diseases), Visha (poisoning) and Vrana (wounds/ulcers), with over ninety references.

Table 1: Review of Daruharidra in Charaka-Samhita.

Sr. No.	Preparation	Indication	Reference no.	Name used
1.	<i>Shirovirechan Dravya</i>	<i>Shirovirechana</i>	<i>Ch. Su. 2/5</i>	<i>Haridre</i>
2.	<i>Kushthadi lepa</i>	<i>Kandu kushtha</i>	<i>Ch. Su. 3/8</i>	<i>Haridre</i>
3.	<i>Kushthadi churna</i>	<i>Kitibha pama</i>	<i>Ch. Su. 3/10</i>	<i>Katankateri</i>
4.	<i>Rasanjanadi lepa</i>	<i>Kushtha</i>	<i>Ch. Su. 3/13</i>	<i>Rasanjana</i>
5.	<i>Haridradi lepa</i>	<i>Kushtha</i>	<i>Ch. Su. 3/14</i>	<i>Ubhaya haridre</i>
6.	<i>Parshwashoola nashaka lepa</i>	<i>Parshwashoola</i>	<i>Ch. Su. 3/25</i>	<i>Haridre</i>
7.	<i>Anu taila</i>	<i>Tridoshnashaka</i>	<i>Ch. Su. 5/63</i>	<i>Darvi</i>
8.	<i>Mustadi kwatha</i>	<i>Kandu, kushtha</i>	<i>Ch. Su. 23/12</i>	<i>Haridre</i>
9.	<i>Vyoshadi saktu</i>	<i>Mudhavata etc.</i>	<i>Ch. Su. 23/19</i>	<i>Haridradvaya</i>
10.	<i>Kwatha</i>	<i>Asthapana vasti</i>	<i>Ch. Vi. 7/17</i>	<i>Daruharidra</i>
11.	<i>Vamanartha dravya</i>	<i>Vamana yoga</i>	<i>Ch. Vi. 8/135</i>	<i>Daruharidra</i>
12.	<i>Chandanadi taila</i>	<i>Jwara-daha</i>	<i>Ch. Ci. 3/258</i>	<i>Kaliyaka</i>
13.	<i>Kwatha</i>	<i>Prameha</i>	<i>Ch. Ci. 6/26</i>	<i>Darvi</i>
14.	<i>Kwatha</i>	<i>Prameha</i>	<i>Ch. Ci. 6/27</i>	<i>Haridre</i>
15.	<i>Kwatha</i>	<i>Prameha</i>	<i>Ch. Ci. 6/28</i>	<i>Darvi</i>
16.	<i>Kwatha</i>	<i>Pittaja Prameha</i>	<i>Ch. Ci. 6/31-32</i>	<i>Katankateri</i>
17.	<i>Phalatrikadi kwatha</i>	<i>Prameha</i>	<i>Ch. Ci. 6/40</i>	<i>Darunisha</i>
18.	<i>Asthapana vasti</i>	<i>Kushtha</i>	<i>Ch. Ci. 7/46</i>	<i>Darvi</i>
19.	<i>Kalka</i>	<i>Kushtha</i>	<i>Ch. Ci. 7/61</i>	<i>Darvi</i>
20.	<i>Triphaladi churna</i>	<i>Kushtha</i>	<i>Ch. Ci. 7/68</i>	<i>Rajanidvaya</i>
21.	<i>Lepa</i>	<i>Kushtha</i>	<i>Ch. Ci. 7/84</i>	<i>Darvi</i>
22.	<i>Siddharthaka snana</i>	<i>Kushtha</i>	<i>Ch. Ci. 7/92</i>	<i>Darvi</i>
23.	<i>Lepa</i>	<i>Kushtha</i>	<i>Ch. Ci. 7/94</i>	<i>Darvi</i>
24.	<i>Kwatha</i>	<i>Kushtha</i>	<i>Ch. Ci. 7/97</i>	<i>Darvi, rasanjana</i>
25.	<i>Kushthadi taila</i>	<i>Kushtha</i>	<i>Ch. Ci. 7/103</i>	<i>Darvi</i>
26.	<i>Tikta ikshavakadi taila</i>	<i>Kushtha</i>	<i>Ch. Ci. 7/108</i>	<i>Haridre</i>
27.	<i>Kanaksheeri taila</i>	<i>Kushtha</i>	<i>Ch. Ci. 7/114</i>	<i>Darvi tvaka</i>
28.	<i>Vipadikahara ghrita taila</i>	<i>Kushtha</i>	<i>Ch. Ci. 7/120</i>	<i>Darvi</i>
29.	<i>Ghrita</i>	<i>Kushtha</i>	<i>Ch. Ci. 7/135</i>	<i>Darvi</i>
30.	<i>Tiktashatpalak ghrita</i>	<i>Kushtha</i>	<i>Ch. Ci. 7/140</i>	<i>Darvi</i>
31.	<i>Mahatiktaka ghrita</i>	<i>Kushtha</i>	<i>Ch. Ci. 7/145</i>	<i>Haridre</i>
32.	<i>Mahakhadir ghrita</i>	<i>Kushtha</i>	<i>Ch. Ci. 7/153</i>	<i>Haridre dvaya</i>
33.	<i>Mukhavairasyanashaka yog</i>	<i>Rajyakshama</i>	<i>Ch. Ci. 8/137</i>	<i>Darvi</i>
34.	<i>Churna</i>	<i>Bhutonmada</i>	<i>Ch. Ci. 9/65</i>	<i>Haridre</i>
35.	<i>Siddharthaka agada</i>	<i>Unmada</i>	<i>Ch. Ci. 9/70</i>	<i>Rajanidvaya</i>
36.	<i>Ghrita</i>	<i>Kshatsheena</i>	<i>Ch. Ci. 11/34</i>	<i>Darvi</i>

37.	<i>Patolmooladi kwatha</i>	<i>Shavathu</i>	<i>Ch. Ci. 12/53</i>	<i>Darvi</i>
38.	<i>Pippalyadi lavana</i>	<i>Udara roga</i>	<i>Ch. Ci. 13/159</i>	<i>Haridre</i>
39.	<i>Kanakarishtha</i>	<i>Arsha</i>	<i>Ch. Ci. 14/160</i>	<i>Daruharidra</i>
40.	<i>Kwatha</i>	<i>Arsha</i>	<i>Ch. Ci. 14/186</i>	<i>Darvi</i>
41.	<i>Churna</i>	<i>Arsha</i>	<i>Ch. Ci. 14/195</i>	<i>Darvi</i>
42.	<i>Churna</i>	<i>Arsha</i>	<i>Ch. Ci. 14/221</i>	<i>Darvi</i>
43.	<i>Hriberadi ghrita</i>	<i>Arsha</i>	<i>Ch. Ci. 14/231</i>	<i>Darvi</i>
44.	<i>Sunishnaka changeri ghrita</i>	<i>Arsha</i>	<i>Ch. Ci. 14/234</i>	<i>Darvi</i>
45.	<i>Vachadi churna</i>	<i>Grahanidosha</i>	<i>Ch. Ci. 15/135</i>	<i>Darvi</i>
46.	<i>Kiratadi churna</i>	<i>Grahanidosha</i>	<i>Ch. Ci. 15/137</i>	<i>Darvi</i>
47.	<i>Haridradi kshara</i>	<i>Mandagni</i>	<i>Ch. Ci. 15/182</i>	<i>Dviharidre</i>
48.	<i>Katukadi ghrita</i>	<i>Pandu</i>	<i>Ch. Ci. 16/47</i>	<i>Haridre</i>
49.	<i>Darvi ghrita</i>	<i>Pandu</i>	<i>Ch. Ci. 16/54</i>	<i>Darvi</i>
50.	<i>Kaliyaka ghrita</i>	<i>Pandu</i>	<i>Ch. Ci. 16/54</i>	<i>Darvi</i>
51.	<i>Kwatha</i>	<i>Pandu</i>	<i>Ch. Ci. 16/63</i>	<i>Darvi</i>
52.	<i>Mandoora vataka</i>	<i>Pandu</i>	<i>Ch. Ci. 16/73</i>	<i>Darvi</i>
53.	<i>Punarnavadi mandoor</i>	<i>Pandu</i>	<i>Ch. Ci. 16/94</i>	<i>Haridre</i>
54.	<i>Darvyadi lepa</i>	<i>Pandu</i>	<i>Ch. Ci. 16/97</i>	<i>Darvi</i>
55.	<i>Triphaladi yoga</i>	<i>Pandu</i>	<i>Ch. Ci. 16/99</i>	<i>Dviharidre</i>
56.	<i>Vyoshadi ghrut</i>	<i>Pandu</i>	<i>Ch. Ci. 16/111</i>	<i>Haridre dvaya</i>
57.	<i>Darvyadi ghrita</i>	<i>Atisara</i>	<i>Ch. Ci. 19/80</i>	<i>Daruharidra</i>
58.	<i>Rasanjana churna</i>	<i>Atisara</i>	<i>Ch. Ci. 19/108</i>	<i>Rasanjana</i>
59.	<i>Patoladi sheeta Kashaya</i>	<i>Visarpa</i>	<i>Ch. Ci. 21/59</i>	<i>Darvi</i>
60.	<i>Pradeha</i>	<i>Kaphaja Visarpa</i>	<i>Ch. Ci. 21/91</i>	<i>Darvi</i>
61.	<i>Churna</i>	<i>Vrana ropana</i>	<i>Ch. Ci. 21/97</i>	<i>Darvi</i>
62.	<i>Kampillakadi taila</i>	<i>Granthi vrana</i>	<i>Ch. Ci. 21/138</i>	<i>Darvi</i>
63.	<i>Mritsanjeevana agada</i>	<i>Visha</i>	<i>Ch. Ci. 23/56</i>	<i>Rajanidvaya</i>
64.	<i>Kshaaragada</i>	<i>Visha</i>	<i>Ch. Ci. 23/101</i>	<i>Rajanidvaya</i>
65.	<i>Churna</i>	<i>Pakvashayagata Visha</i>	<i>Ch. Ci. 23/185</i>	<i>Rajanidvaya</i>
66.	<i>Chandanadi yoga</i>	<i>Visha</i>	<i>Ch. Ci. 23/191</i>	<i>Haridradvaya</i>
67.	<i>Kalka</i>	<i>Vasuki sarpadansha</i>	<i>Ch. Ci. 23/198</i>	<i>Haridradvaya</i>
68.	<i>Vachadi yoga</i>	<i>Visha</i>	<i>Ch. Ci. 23/212</i>	<i>Rajanidavya</i>
69.	<i>Lepa</i>	<i>Visha</i>	<i>Ch. Ci. 23/216</i>	<i>Dviharidre</i>
70.	-	<i>Visha peedita pashu</i>	<i>Ch. Ci. 23/231</i>	<i>Haridradvaya</i>
71.	<i>Vrana shodhaka Kashaya</i>	<i>Vranashodhana</i>	<i>Ch. Ci. 25/84</i>	<i>Darvi</i>
72.	<i>Pralepa</i>	<i>Vranashodhana</i>	<i>Ch. Ci. 25/85</i>	<i>Dviharidre</i>
73.	<i>Chandanadi lepa</i>	<i>Vrana</i>	<i>Ch. Ci. 25/88</i>	<i>Darvi</i>
74.	<i>Durvadi taila</i>	<i>Vrana ropana</i>	<i>Ch. Ci. 25/93</i>	<i>Darvi</i>
75.	<i>Tvakvishuddhikar lepa</i>	<i>Vrana</i>	<i>Ch. Ci. 25/114</i>	<i>Rajanidvaya</i>
76.	<i>Ervarubeejadi churna</i>	<i>Mutrakrichra</i>	<i>Ch. Ci. 26/53</i>	<i>Darvi</i>
77.	<i>Pippalyadi kawal graha</i>	<i>Mutraroga</i>	<i>Ch. Ci. 26/188</i>	<i>Darvi</i>
78.	<i>Tejohvadi churna</i>	<i>Manjana</i>	<i>Ch. Ci. 26/191</i>	<i>Darvi</i>
79.	<i>Peetaka churna</i>	<i>Kantharoga</i>	<i>Ch. Ci. 26/197</i>	<i>Darvi</i>
80.	<i>Mridvikadi churna</i>	<i>Kantharoga</i>	<i>Ch. Ci. 26/198</i>	<i>Darvi</i>
81.	<i>Pathadi churna</i>	<i>Kantharoga</i>	<i>Ch. Ci. 26/199</i>	<i>Rasanjana</i>
82.	<i>Katukadi kwatha</i>	<i>Kantharoga</i>	<i>Ch. Ci. 26/201</i>	<i>Darvi</i>
83.	<i>Darvyadi rasakriya</i>	<i>Mukha roga</i>	<i>Ch. Ci. 26/202</i>	<i>Darvi</i>

84.	<i>Ashchyotana</i>	<i>Pittaja netra roga</i>	<i>Ch. Ci. 26/238</i>	<i>Darvi</i>
85.	<i>Amritadi varti</i>	<i>Tridoshaja netraroga</i>	<i>Ch. Ci. 26/243</i>	<i>Darvi</i>
86.	<i>Kalka</i>	<i>Urustambha</i>	<i>Ch. Ci. 27/31</i>	<i>Dviharidre</i>
87.	<i>Prapaundrikadi lepa</i>	<i>Vatarakta</i>	<i>Ch. Ci. 29/134</i>	<i>Darvi</i>
88.	<i>Lepa</i>	<i>Vatarakta</i>	<i>Ch. Ci. 29/149</i>	<i>Rajanidvaya</i>
89.	<i>Rasnadi niruha</i>	<i>Krimi, kushtha</i>	<i>Ch. Si. 3/61</i>	<i>Darvi</i>
90.	<i>Vidangadi taila</i>	<i>Krimi, kushtha</i>	<i>Ch. Si. 4/20</i>	<i>Darvi</i>

Sushruta Samhita emphasizes its role in surgical and ophthalmic contexts, enlisting it under Haridradi (group beginning with Haridra), Mustadi (group beginning with Musta), Lakshadi (group beginning with Laksha), DaruHaridradi (group beginning with DaruHaridra) and Tikta Varga (bitter group), with about sixty-one mentions, particularly in Vrana (wounds/ulcers), Kushta (skin disorders), Meha (urinary disorders), Gulma (abdominal lumps/tumors), Bhagandara (fistula-in-ano) and Netra Roga (eye diseases).

Table 2: Review of DaruHaridra in Sushruta-Samhita.

Sr. No.	Preparation	Indication	Reference no.	Name used
1.	-	<i>Kram-viruddha</i>	<i>Su. Su. 20/14</i>	<i>Darvi</i>
2.	<i>Ghrita</i>	-	<i>Su. Su. 36/17</i>	<i>Haridradvaya</i>
3.	<i>Ropana ghrita</i>	<i>Ropana</i>	<i>Su. Su. 36/26</i>	<i>Haridre</i>
4.	<i>Ropana taila</i>	<i>Ropana</i>	<i>Su. Su. 36/27</i>	<i>Haridre</i>
5.	<i>Asava</i>	-	<i>Su. Su. 40/438</i>	<i>Darvi</i>
6.	<i>Taila</i>	<i>Vrana ropana</i>	<i>Su. Ci. 2/68</i>	<i>Darvi</i>
7.	<i>Taila</i>	<i>Sadhyavrana</i>	<i>Su. Ci. 2/75</i>	<i>Haridre</i>
8.	<i>Taila</i>	<i>Sadhyavrana</i>	<i>Su. Ci. 2/90</i>	<i>Haridre</i>
9.	<i>Kwatha</i>	<i>Gulma, meha etc.</i>	<i>Su. Ci. 5/42</i>	<i>Darvi</i>
10.	<i>Kalka</i>	<i>Bhagandara</i>	<i>Su. Ci. 8/41</i>	<i>Haridre</i>
11.	<i>Taila</i>	<i>Bhagandara</i>	<i>Su. Ci. 8/44</i>	<i>Rajanidvaya</i>
12.	<i>Mahaneela ghrita</i>	<i>Kushtha</i>	<i>Su. Ci. 9/35</i>	<i>Darvi</i>
13.	<i>Lepa</i>	<i>Kushtha, shvitra</i>	<i>Su. Ci. 9/28</i>	<i>Haridre</i>
14.	<i>Churna</i>	<i>Kushtha</i>	<i>Su. Ci. 9/46</i>	<i>Haridre</i>
15.	<i>Ghrita</i>	<i>Kushtha</i>	<i>Su. Ci. 9/49</i>	<i>Haridradvaya</i>
16.	<i>Vajraka taila</i>	<i>Kushtha</i>	<i>Su. Ci. 9/55</i>	<i>Rajanidvaya</i>
17.	<i>Mahavajraka taila</i>	<i>Kushtha</i>	<i>Su. Ci. 9/57</i>	<i>Dvi haridre</i>
18.	<i>Kwatha</i>	<i>Pishti meha</i>	<i>Su. Ci. 11/9</i>	<i>DaruHaridra</i>
19.	<i>Karanjadi ghrita</i>	<i>Dushta vrana etc.</i>	<i>Su. Ci. 16/17</i>	<i>Dvi haridre</i>
20.	<i>Taila</i>	<i>Kaphavatajanya nadivrana</i>	<i>Su. Ci. 17/41</i>	<i>Rajanidvaya</i>
21.	<i>Churna</i>	<i>Updansha</i>	<i>Su. Ci. 19/40</i>	<i>Darvi</i>
22.	<i>Lepa</i>	<i>Kachu, pama etc.</i>	<i>Su. Ci. 20/18</i>	<i>Darvi</i>
23.	<i>Churna</i>	<i>Karnapali roga</i>	<i>Su. Ci. 25/20</i>	<i>Rajanidvaya</i>
24.	<i>Ghrita</i>	<i>Vyanga, neelika etc.</i>	<i>Su. Ci. 26/38</i>	<i>Dviharidre</i>
25.	<i>Triphaladi taila</i>	<i>Sthaulya, alasya etc.</i>	<i>Su. Ci. 37/33</i>	<i>Nishadvaya</i>

26.	<i>Lepa</i>	<i>Visha</i>	<i>Su. Ka. 1/54</i>	<i>Kaliyaka</i>
27.	<i>Ajeya ghrita</i>	<i>Vishaghna</i>	<i>Su. Ka. 2/48</i>	<i>Haridrdvaya</i>
28.	<i>Yavagu</i>	<i>Visha</i>	<i>Su. Ka. 3/45</i>	<i>Rajanidvaya</i>
29.	<i>Maha agada</i>	<i>Sarva-visha</i>	<i>Su. Ka. 5/62</i>	<i>Haridre</i>
30.	<i>Agada</i>	<i>Mushika visha</i>	<i>Su. Ka. 5/82</i>	<i>Darvi</i>
31.	<i>Kalyanaka sarpi</i>	<i>Sarva-visha</i>	<i>Su. Ka. 6/9</i>	<i>Rajanyo</i>
32.	<i>Mahasugandhi agda raj</i>	<i>Sarva-visha</i>	<i>Su. Ka. 6/19</i>	<i>Haridre</i>
33.	<i>Sanshaman yog</i>	<i>Mushika visha</i>	<i>Su. Ka. 7/39</i>	<i>Rasanjana</i>
34.	<i>Kusthadi agada</i>	<i>Trikantaka visha</i>	<i>Su. Ka. 8/47</i>	<i>Haridrdvaya</i>
35.	<i>Kumkumadi agada</i>	<i>Shatpadi visha</i>	<i>Su. Ka. 8/49</i>	<i>Rajanidvaya</i>
36.	<i>Ghrita</i>	<i>Pittabhishyanda</i>	<i>Su. Ut. 10/4</i>	<i>Darvi</i>
37.	<i>Anjana</i>	<i>Sirotpata</i>	<i>Su. Ut. 12/16</i>	<i>Darvi</i>
38.	<i>Anjana</i>	<i>Raktabhishyanda</i>	<i>Su. Ut. 12/19</i>	<i>Darvi</i>
39.	<i>Kashmaryadi Anjana</i>	<i>Pitta vidagdh Drishti</i>	<i>Su. Ut. 17/15</i>	<i>Darvi</i>
40.	<i>Naktandhyahara Anjana</i>	<i>Naktandhya</i>	<i>Su. Ut. 17/17</i>	<i>Kshande</i>
41.	<i>Raskriya</i>	<i>Pittaja timira</i>	<i>Su. Ut. 17/39</i>	<i>Rasanjana</i>
42.	<i>Bhadrodaya Anjana</i>	<i>Raj Anjana</i>	<i>Su. Ut. 18/96</i>	<i>Darvi</i>
43.	<i>Manahshiladi Anjana</i>	<i>Kandu, timira etc.</i>	<i>Su. Ut. 18/100</i>	<i>Rajanyo</i>
44.	<i>Gutika Anjana</i>	<i>Kununaka</i>	<i>Su. Ut. 19/15</i>	<i>Darvi</i>
45.	<i>Patoladi ghrita</i>	<i>Kamla, jwara etc.</i>	<i>Su. Ut. 39/50</i>	<i>Darvi</i>
46.	<i>Patoladi ghrita</i>	<i>Jwara</i>	<i>Su. Ut. 39/227</i>	<i>Darvi</i>
47.	<i>Kalyana ghrita</i>	<i>Jeerna jwara</i>	<i>Su. Ut. 39/231</i>	<i>Rajanidvaya</i>
48.	<i>Triphaladi ghrita</i>	<i>Jwara, visarpa</i>	<i>Su. Ut. 39/245</i>	<i>Rajanidvaya</i>
49.	<i>Kalingadi vinshati yoga</i>	<i>Atisara</i>	<i>Su. Ut. 40/40</i>	<i>Haridre</i>
50.	<i>Kalingadi vinshati yoga</i>	<i>Atisara</i>	<i>Su. Ut. 40/42</i>	<i>Haridre</i>
51.	<i>Kwatha</i>	<i>Pitta pachana</i>	<i>Su. Ut. 40/62</i>	<i>Rasanajan, haridredvaya</i>
52.	<i>Mustadi yoga</i>	<i>Pittatisara</i>	<i>Su. Ut. 40/64</i>	<i>Haridredvaya</i>
53.	<i>Mustadi yoga</i>	<i>Pittatisara</i>	<i>Su. Ut. 40/66</i>	<i>Haridradvaya</i>
54.	<i>Darvyadi ghrita</i>	<i>Sannipataja pittatisara</i>	<i>Su. Ut. 40/78</i>	<i>Darvi</i>
55.	<i>Lodhradi putapaka</i>	<i>Kaphapittatisara</i>	<i>Su. Ut. 40/87</i>	<i>Darvi</i>
56.	<i>Darvyadi ghrita</i>	<i>Raktmalatisara</i>	<i>Su. Ut. 40/105</i>	<i>Darvi</i>
57.	<i>Harenukadi yog</i>	<i>Kasa</i>	<i>Su. Ut. 52/19</i>	<i>Haridre</i>
58.	<i>Vyoshadi Anjana</i>	<i>Visuchika</i>	<i>Su. Ut. 56/18</i>	<i>Haridre</i>
59.	<i>Leha</i>	<i>Arochaka</i>	<i>Su. Ut. 57/11</i>	<i>Rajanidvaya</i>
60.	<i>Kwatha</i>	<i>Arochaka</i>	<i>Su. Ut. 57/16</i>	<i>Mustadigana</i>
61.	<i>Naktmaladi varti</i>	<i>Graha dosha</i>	<i>Su. Ut. 60/44</i>	<i>Haridre</i>

Ashtanga Hridaya (7th century CE compendium of Ayurveda) balances both internal and external applications, citing it in seventy-one instances across conditions such as Arsha (piles), Prameha (urinary disorders), Pandu (anemia), Kamala (jaundice), Visarpa (erysipelas/cellulitis), Visha (poisoning), Unmada (psychosis), Apasmara (epilepsy) and Mukha Roga (oral diseases).

Table 3: Review of *Daruharidra* in *Ashtang Hridayam*.

Sr. No.	Preparation	Indication	Reference no.	Name used
1.	-	Visha vikara	Ah. Su. 7/25	Haridre
2.	Anu taila	Urdhvajatrugata rog	Ah. Su. 20/37	Darvi
3.	Mukha lepa	Shishira ritu	Ah. Su. 22/19	Darvi
4.	-	Snana	Ah. Sh. 1/62	Darvi
5.	Haritaki rasayana	Kasa	Ah. Ci. 3/31	Haridre
6.	Kwatha	Raktarsh	Ah. Ci. 8/103	Darvi
7.	Changeri ghrita	Arsha	Ah. Ci. 8/139	Darvi
8.	Churna	Atisara	Ah. Ci. 9/57	Darvi
9.	-	Atisara	Ah. Ci. 9/62	Katankateri
10.	Ghrita	Raktatisara	Ah. Ci. 9/89	Darvi
11.	Patoladi churna	Grahani	Ah. Ci. 10/35	Darvi
12.	Haridradi Bhasma	Grahani	Ah. Ci. 10/57	Dvi haridre
13.	-	Pittaja mutraghata	Ah. Ci. 11/8	Darvi
14.	Kwatha	Prameha	Ah. Ci. 12/6	Darvi
15.	Kwatha	Kaphaja Prameha	Ah. Ci. 12/7	Darvi
16.	Ghrita	Pittaja vidradhi	Ah. Ci. 13/5	Dvinisha
17.	Mandoora vataka	Pandu	Ah. Ci. 16/16	Darvi
18.	Ghrita	Pandu	Ah. Ci. 16/36	Dvirajani
19.	Swarasa	Kamla	Ah. Ci. 16/44	Darvi
20.	Patoladi kwatha	Pittaja shotha	Ah. Ci. 17/31	Darvi
21.	Kwatha	Visarpa	Ah. Ci. 18/7	Darvi
22.	Taila	Vrana ropana	Ah. Ci. 18/35	Darvi
23.	Tiktaka ghrita	Kushtha	Ah. Ci. 19/2	Darvi
24.	Mahatikta ghrita	Kushtha	Ah. Ci. 19/8	Rajanyo
25.	Darvyadi kwatha	Kushtha	Ah. Ci. 19/38	Darvi
26.	Pathadi yoga	Arsha, Prameha etc.	Ah. Ci. 19/40	Darvi
27.	Mustadi kwatha	Kushtha	Ah. Ci. 19/59	Darvi
28.	Shveta karveeradi lepa	Kushtha	Ah. Ci. 19/62	Darvi
29.	Nimbadi ubtana	Kushtha	Ah. Ci. 19/65	Haridre
30.	Mustadi avchurna	Dad, kandu, kitibha	Ah. Ci. 19/67	Katankateri
31.	Gugguladi gharshan	Kushtha	Ah. Ci. 19/72	Ubhaya haridre
32.	Jeevantydi ghrita-taila	Kushtha	Ah. Ci. 19/77	Darvi
33.	Vajraka taila	Kushtha	Ah. Ci. 19/79	Dviharidre
34.	Lepa	Vatarakta	Ah. Ci. 22/28	Darvi
35.	Siddharthaka taila agada	Visha, unmada	Ah. Ut. 5/10	Rajanidvaya
36.	Siddhartha guda vatika	Dushta vrana, unmada	Ah. Ut. 5/15	Nishadvaya
37.	Mahabhutarav ghrita	Bhutonmada	Ah. Ut. 5/20	Nishayugm
38.	Anjana	Yaksha graha	Ah. Ut. 5/36	Haridredvaya
39.	Mahapanchgavya ghrita	Apasmar	Ah. Ut. 7/19	Dvinisha
40.	Kwatha	Pothaki	Ah. Ut. 9/22	Dvinisha
41.	Lepa	Kukunaka	Ah. Ut. 9/32	Dvinisha
42.	Kwatha	Timira, pilla roga etc	Ah. Ut. 11/22	Dvinisha
43.	Patoladi ghrita	Timira	Ah. Ut. 13/6	Darvi

44.	<i>Taila</i>	<i>Timira</i>	<i>Ah. Ut. 13/69</i>	<i>Dvinisha</i>
45.	<i>Taila</i>	<i>Timira</i>	<i>Ah. Ut. 13/92</i>	<i>Darvi</i>
46.	<i>Anjana</i>	<i>Abhishyanda</i>	<i>Ah. Ut. 16/25</i>	<i>Darvi</i>
47.	<i>Ashchyotana</i>	<i>Akshishopha</i>	<i>Ah. Ut. 16/33</i>	<i>Darvi</i>
48.	<i>Lakshadi masi</i>	<i>Pilla roga</i>	<i>Ah. Ut. 16/57</i>	<i>Darvi</i>
49.	<i>Sneha</i>	<i>Karnapali vardhaka</i>	<i>Ah. Ut. 18/56</i>	<i>Rajanyo</i>
50.	<i>Kwatha</i>	<i>Kantha roga</i>	<i>Ah. Ut. 22/55</i>	<i>Darvi</i>
51.	-	<i>Kantha roga</i>	<i>Ah. Ut. 22/56</i>	<i>Darvi, rasanjana</i>
52.	<i>Gutika</i>	<i>Mukha roga</i>	<i>Ah. Ut. 22/81</i>	<i>Haridradvaya</i>
53.	<i>Ubtana</i>	<i>Vyanga, nilika etc.</i>	<i>Ah. Ut. 22/87</i>	<i>Darvi</i>
54.	<i>Khadiradi gutika</i>	<i>Mukharoga</i>	<i>Ah. Ut. 22/92</i>	<i>Dvinisha</i>
55.	<i>Kshudradi kawala</i>	<i>Mukharoga</i>	<i>Ah. Ut. 22/97</i>	<i>Darvi</i>
56.	<i>Pathadi manjana</i>	<i>Mukharoga</i>	<i>Ah. Ut. 22/98</i>	<i>Darvi</i>
57.	<i>Peetaka churna</i>	<i>Danta-mukha-gala roga</i>	<i>Ah. Ut. 22/100</i>	<i>Darvi</i>
58.	<i>Patoladi kwatha</i>	<i>Mukharoga</i>	<i>Ah. Ut. 22/104</i>	<i>Dvinisha</i>
59.	<i>Darvi ghana kwatha</i>	<i>Mukhapaka</i>	<i>Ah. Ut. 22/105</i>	<i>Darvi</i>
60.	<i>Jatyadi ghrita</i>	<i>Vrana</i>	<i>Ah. Ut. 25/67</i>	<i>Darvi</i>
61.	<i>Taila</i>	<i>Sadhyavrana</i>	<i>Ah. Ut. 26/26</i>	<i>Darvi</i>
62.	<i>Talishadi taila</i>	<i>Sadhyavrana</i>	<i>Ah. Ut. 26/35</i>	<i>Haridre</i>
63.	<i>Lepa</i>	<i>Vyanga, nilika</i>	<i>Ah. Ut. 32/22</i>	<i>Haridradvaya</i>
64.	<i>Manjishthadi Sneha</i>	<i>Vyanga, nilika</i>	<i>Ah. Ut. 32/31</i>	<i>Haridradvaya</i>
65.	<i>Yavagu</i>	<i>Visha</i>	<i>Ah. Ut. 35/21</i>	<i>Haridre</i>
66.	<i>Padma agada</i>	<i>Luta visha</i>	<i>Ah. Ut. 37/70</i>	<i>Dvinisha</i>
67.	<i>Champaka agada</i>	<i>Luta visha</i>	<i>Ah. Ut. 37/71</i>	<i>Haridradvaya</i>
68.	<i>Mandar agada</i>	<i>Luta visha</i>	<i>Ah. Ut. 37/73</i>	<i>Darvi</i>
69.	<i>Ghrita</i>	<i>Akhu visha</i>	<i>Ah. Ut. 38/25</i>	<i>Dvinisha</i>
70.	<i>Lepa</i>	<i>Nakha-danta visha</i>	<i>Ah. Ut. 36/39</i>	<i>Rajanyo</i>
71.	<i>Naladadi ghrita Rasayana</i>	<i>Rasayana karma</i>	<i>Ah. Ut. 39/46</i>	<i>Haridre</i>

Ashtanga Sangraha (7th century CE encyclopedic text of Ayurveda) highlights its incorporation into Shodhana (purification therapies), Visha Chikitsa (toxicology/poison management), Jvara (fever), Sthulya (obesity) and Snana (bath/ablution) regimens, with at least thirteen references. Across all texts, Daruharidra is consistently described as possessing Tikta Rasa (bitter taste), Katu Vipaka (pungent post-digestive effect), Ushna Virya (hot potency) and Kapha-Pitta Hara (alleviator of Kapha and Pitta doshas), underscoring its pharmacological relevance in metabolic, dermatological, ophthalmic and toxicological conditions. Comparative analysis demonstrates both continuity and contextual divergence in its usage, reflecting the evolving therapeutic applications of Daruharidra from internal medicine to surgical, lifestyle, and preventive domains.

The Sharangdhara Samhita (13th century A.D.), authored by Acharya Sharangdhara, grandson of Raghavdeva and son of Damodara, is regarded as one of the three principal texts of the

Laghu Trayi along with Madhava Nidana and Bhavaprakasha. Structured into three Khandas with 32 chapters, this compendium outlines numerous therapeutic practices. Within it, Daruharidra finds repeated mention, both in single-drug prescriptions and as a constituent of compound formulations, reflecting its broad utility in clinical applications of the period.

The Bhavaprakasha (16th century A.D.), written by Acharya Bhavamishra, is another influential treatise of the Laghu Trayi. Divided into Purva Khanda, Madhyama Khanda, and Uttara Khanda, it covers diverse aspects of Ayurvedic science. In this text, Bhavamishra has provided a detailed account of Daruharidra, carefully noting its properties, therapeutic actions, and extensive use across a wide range of diseases. Its frequent inclusion in polyherbal preparations further demonstrates its versatility and valued role in Ayurvedic formulations.

Together, these two treatises emphasize the continuity of Daruharidra's importance during the medieval era, highlighting its enduring pharmacological significance and consistent therapeutic relevance across Ayurvedic practice.

Period / Text	Author	Century / Era	Classification / Mention of Daruharidra	Context / Notes
Vedic Texts	Vedic sages	c.1500-1000 BCE	General mention of medicinal plants	Used for treatment of common ailments
Charaka Samhita	Agnivesha, revised by Charaka & Dridhabala	c. 1000 BCE - 200 CE	Arshoghna Mahakashaya, Kandughna Mahakashaya, Lekhaniya Mahakashaya, Tikta Skandha	Therapeutic use in multiple formulations
Sushruta Samhita	Sushruta, later edited by Nagarjuna	c. 1000 BCE - 500 CE	Haridradi, Mustadi, Lakshadi, Daruharidradi gana, Rasaut-anjandi gana, Tikta Varga	Described for diverse ailments, surgical adjuncts
Ashtanga Hridaya	Vagbhata	7th Century CE	Asanadi, Haridradi, Mustadi, Nasya, Vachadi, Rasaut-anjandi ganas	Noted for multipurpose therapeutic uses
Ashtanga Sangraha	Vagbhata	7th Century CE	Various contexts	Holistic description across 8 branches
Sharangadhara	Sharangadhara	13th	Several formulations	Widely used in

Samhita		Century CE		compound preparations
Bhavaprakasha	Bhavamishra	16th Century CE	Detailed pharmacological properties and uses	Multipurpose medicinal use
Bhela Samhita	Bhela, disciple of Atreya	6th Century BCE	Various formulations	Unique references, disease management
Harita Samhita	Harita	Early medieval period	Annapana, Arishta, Chikitsa, Kalpa, Sutra, Sharira sthanas	Detailed pharmacological properties and uses
Kashyapa Samhita	Vridha Jivaka, revived by Vatsya	600-1000 CE	Pediatric formulations	Major role in Kaumarbhritya (pediatrics)
Siddhasara Samhita	Ravigupta	7th Century CE	Various mentions	Described for disorders, compound use

DISCUSSION

The continuous mention of Daruharidra across nearly all major Ayurvedic treatises demonstrates its therapeutic centrality. While early Vedic references were general, systematic classifications began in the Samhita period, where Daruharidra was included in specific ganas (groups of drugs) like Arshoghna (anti-hemorrhoidal), Kandughna (anti-pruritic), and Lekhaniya (scraping/anti-obesity). Surgical contexts in the Sushruta Samhita highlight its use in wound healing and infection control, suggesting an early recognition of its antimicrobial action. Later texts like Bhavaprakasha refined its pharmacological profile, reflecting continuity as well as innovation in Ayurvedic pharmacology.

The consistency of its description across centuries indicates not only its empirical effectiveness but also the preservation of knowledge within the Ayurvedic tradition. Interestingly, the pediatric emphasis in Kashyapa Samhita and the surgical focus in Sushruta Samhita highlight the plant's adaptability to varied contexts. This wide applicability makes Daruharidra an ideal candidate for bridging ancient insights with modern pharmacological validation.

CONCLUSION

Daruharidra emerges as one of the most consistently mentioned and therapeutically versatile herbs in classical Ayurveda. Its documentation from the Vedic hymns to medieval texts underscores its enduring significance in disease management. The master table presented here

consolidates textual evidence, offering a valuable resource for researchers. Moving forward, critical correlation between these classical references and modern pharmacological findings may provide a deeper understanding of Daruharidra's potential in contemporary healthcare, while honoring its historical legacy.

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